

PECULIARITIES OF COPYING AND REPRODUCTION OF MANUSCRIPT BOOKS.

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Annotation: This article provides information about the activities of early libraries in the Middle Ages, methods of reproduction of manuscript books, librarianship during the Khanate period, and bookkeeping during the Khanate period in the works of foreign scholars.

Key words: book, bookmaking, khanates, era, manuscripts, calligraphy, tradition, knowledge, book copying, scientist, country.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada o'rta aslarda dastlabki kutubxonalarning faoliyati, qo'lyozma kitoblarni ko'paytirish usullari, xonliklar davridagi kutubxonachilik ishi va xorij olimlarining asarlarida xonliklar davridagi kitobat ishi haqida ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: kitob, kitobat ishi, xonliklar, davr, qo'lyozma asarlar, xattotlik, an'ana, bilim, kitob ko'chirish, olim, mamlakat.

Аннотация: В статье представлены сведения о деятельности ранних библиотек в средние века, способах воспроизведения рукописных книг, библиотечном деле в период ханства и бухгалтерском учете в период ханства в трудах зарубежных ученых.

Ключевые слова: книга, книгопечатание, ханства, эпоха, рукописи, каллиграфия, традиция, знание, переписывание книг, учёный, страна.

Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts[1]. In the Middle Ages, reproduction of manuscript books was carried out in several ways. Copying manuscripts for oneself was considered one of the simplest methods. In this case, the book was reproduced for educational purposes, scientific purposes, and personal use for other purposes. One of the reasons for the large number of written books in the Muslim cultural world is because the majority of the population, especially the urban population, learns or improves their knowledge with the help of books. Let's stay. - a large number of young officials, representatives of the lower, middle and upper classes of Muslim priests, urban artisans and merchants - all were educated with the help of books.

All scholars. Fine arts and artistic knowledge. Enthusiasts also copied books for personal use, but often the majority of manuscripts were originally copied for personal use or for sale. regardless - ultimately. but several decades

after the move, it became a commodity for sale, and sometimes even changed owners a dozen times. In cases where the manuscript is the private property of an individual. reproduced with permission of the copyright holder. If the manuscript is owned by a particular public library. copying by permission of this librarian. According to the tradition of Muslim communities in libraries, libraries under madrassas and mosques, individuals could copy any book for themselves free of charge. According to another wonderful tradition practiced in During that period, the owners of the libraries, who were engaged in collecting books all their lives, bequeathed them to the public libraries of the Muslim communities or to the libraries of madrasahs and mosques. They even made a separate record of how much money they would allocate from their real estate to the purchase of paper and stationery in their wills. This paper and stationery should be given free of charge to students who want to copy the donated books. However, most of the handwritten books in the book market were copied by calligraphers. In order to become a master of calligraphy, in addition to literacy, it was required to write quickly, accurately and fluently, to have a deep knowledge of Arabic writing styles, and the textological features of oriental manuscripts. The calligraphers of the peasant community, especially the middle-class calligraphers, were prepared in the same way as in other professions, in the hands of a calligrapher who was a master of his profession, in the “master-apprentice” method. were considered the main producers. Therefore, it is appropriate to say that the method of book reproduction (book copying) according to individual orders was the most common method in Turonzamin medieval society. In this case, a handwritten book copies were made by calligraphers who worked alone or together with their students in their home workshops. Such books were covered in special workshops of sakhhs. Some sakhhs workshops had their own calligraphers. The division of labor determined by the general situation and the demand in it entered the field of book production as well. But such a commonality was more characteristic of the first classical period of copying and reproduction of manuscript books, when decoration of manuscript books was not paid as much attention as it was in the 15th century. In Turonzamin cities, the demand for written books increased during the dark and peaceful years of peace. In response to this, relatively stable enterprises of calligraphers, lavvohs (book decorators) and scribes appeared in these cities. In such enterprise associations according to the orders of the average person. Most of Turonzamin's manuscript books made in calligraphy workshops or calligrapher's houses are decorated quite simply.

Sakhofs' workshops sometimes take advantage of the opportunity to provide the customer with an experienced calligrapher working individually according to an employment contract or other contract, which allows them to be classified as business associations of book workshops in some cases.

Activities of libraries. Manuscript books were reproduced in special workshops - bookstores near the palace. Libraries are kings. regional governors. established under the family libraries of great nobles. As a rule, for your library. specially decorated books were prepared. These books, copied in the most famous and beautiful methods of Arabic script, with pages decorated with miniatures, and covers decorated with geometric griffin method and plant-like Islamic methods, are in most cases of special artistic value. Became rare examples of book art. Such books were created by the work of famous calligraphers, painters, painters and scribes who were attracted to the palace workshops for a good price. But the books created in such workshops did not determine the main volume of book products on the market. of course. These books did not leave the private library of the rich owner of the palace. According to the legacy of the Zoroastrian cultural world from the time of Khusrau the Great (531-579) and revived in the Muslim cultural world during the reign of Caliph Kharun ar-Rashid (786-809). Many rulers of Turonzamin gathered in their palaces writers, scientists, historians, chroniclers, jurisprudents, khafiz, and book masters. those who founded their own libraries or filled the dynastic libraries inherited from their ancestors with new books, copying the written books. who opened workshops engaged in their repair.

Khorezmshah Ma'mun ibn Mamun (reigned 997 - 1017) successfully transferred the traditions of the famous "Bayt ul-Hikma" - medieval academy in Baghdad to Turonzamin. He gathered the best scientific forces of that time in Gurganj. He created all conditions for them to engage in scientific research. In the palace of Ma'mun ibn Ma'mun, there was a large library of manuscripts in Arabic, Persian and Turkish languages, as well as a library where book masters, cartographers and scribes prepared manuscript books according to the orders of the king and his servants. In Gurganj, the great scholar Beruni continued his scientific activity, here the mathematician Ibn Iraq, the philosopher and translator Abu Sahl al-Mashikhi (died 1010), the poet, literary critic and historian Abu Mansur al-Saalibi (961-1038). doctor Abulkhayr al-Khammar (942-1030) created. The great scholar Ibn Sina also lived in Mamun's palace for some time. Scholars and virtuous people from many cities of the Near and Middle East gathered for the literary, musical and scientific gatherings,

discussions and debates organized by Mamun from time to time. Among others. According to the Strategy of Reforms, the successful implementation of huge changes in all spheres of public life largely depends on the level of legal consciousness and legal culture of people.[2] Ibn Miskavayh, the author of treatises on philosophy and ethics and the “Book of People’s Experiences”, a great historian and philosopher, Ibn Miskavayh, also participated in these meetings. Historical sources in Bukhara during the Somonites (10th century), Shaybani and Ashtarkhanids (16th - 17th centuries). During the Bukhara Khanate (XVIII - XIX centuries). In Samarkand during the reign of Amir Temur and his grandson Ulugbek, in Herat Shahrukh. Boysunkur. During the time of Khusayn Boykaro and Alisher Navoi (XV - XVI centuries), Marv (XI - XII centuries). In Kok (XVIII - XIX centuries) it is evidence that the palace libraries were active in reproduction and copying of manuscript books. In the 11th - 12th centuries, Khorezmshahs also had their own libraries. This tradition was continued during the Khiva Khanate (XVI - XIX centuries). The information about the library of Herat in the book “Tazkiratush Shuaro” of Davlatshakh Samarkandi gives a certain idea about the palace libraries and the organization of work in them. In the 20s of the 15th century, according to the instructions of his father Shahrukh Mirza, Boysunqur Mirza established a library in Herat. 40 masters of book art work under the leadership of the famous calligrapher Maulana Jafar Tabrizi. Calligraphers, secretaries, miniature painters, decorators - painters, goldsmiths - jewelers, sakhhaf - cover makers, repairmen and other masters work here. Along with the above-mentioned laws, the library-information activity has its own characteristics.[3] The selection of the most important and unique literary works for copying was carried out with the participation and leadership of linguists, literary scholars, experts in the literary heritage of various Eastern nations. The first page of such books is usually stamped with a book mark (ex-libris) – Shakhrukh’s seal. In 1426 Different versions of the work “Shakhnoma” written by Ferdavsi were collected and 435 years after its creation, its perfect text was compiled for the first time and copied again in the library of Boysunqur Mirza. In other words, in order to carry out this work, selected manuscripts of “Shakhnoma” in the library of Herat were compared and a textual study was conducted from the point of view of that time. the manuscript has been preserved and is now kept in the treasury of the Gulistan Library in Tehran.[4]

E. Bertels, a well-known Russian orientalist who highly appreciated the great work done by 15th-century linguists and literary scholars, notes, among

other things: we wouldn't even have the text. In the 19th century, a large bookstore was engaged in the reproduction and copying of manuscript books, as well as the lithographic printing of books. During the reign of Mukhammad Rakhim Khan II (1865 - 1910), who wrote poems under the pseudonym Feruz, interest in artistic creativity, translation and literary reading developed here. In the summer of 1908, the Russian Turkish scholar A. Samoylovich, who visited Khiva Khanate, left valuable information about the state of the library work in Khorezm. In his "Brief Report" he described in detail his meetings and conversations with the khan, his courtiers and calligraphers, his visits to the khan's library, bookshop and lithographic book workshop. Khiva II is an enlightened patron of science and art. He expressed his willingness to help me in the scientific study of his country, and even allowed me access to his private book archives and peruse them. I Khan's Ark and Tozabog I visited both libraries in the city twice, focusing on manuscripts written in Turkic languages. In the summer, I twice visited the lithography workshop of Khan 209, which was moved to Tozabog. [5] You will get acquainted with the new copies of manuscripts and printed publications that are continuously prepared by the whole state. For example, in many manuscript copies of Alisher Navoi's "Chor Devan" (another name is "Khazayin ul-Maoni" – "Treasure of Meanings") copied in Kok, the last words of the calligraphers it is mentioned that the book was copied according to the decree of Kokan Khan Mukhammad Ali Khan. The letter described in the manuscript number 1709 kept in the fund of the Institute of Oriental Studies named after Abu Rayhan Beruni of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan is one of the most complete and detailed information about the above-mentioned situation. According to the decree issued by Khan of Kokan Mukhammad Ali Khan in 1838, Mukhammad Siddik Tunkatar was assigned the task of copying 300 copies of Alisher Navoi's "Chor Devon" by the best calligraphers of the Khanate. According to the conclusion, Mukhammad Alikhan implemented this great cultural event in the life of the country based on the advice of his mother, the poetess Nodirabegim. "Chor devon" man 300 copies were made in six hunts, decorated by plaques and painters. brought to book status by sahhof's. It is known that "Khazayin ul-Maoni" collection of divans was created by Alisher Navoi in 1492. he created it on the basis of sorting, creative processing and adding new works to the poems from his four divans composed in previous years. Copies of "Khazayin ul-Maani" books of different sizes of four divan texts were prepared in Mukhammad Ali Khan library in large format. Seven copies of this book, which are currently stored in the fund of the Institute

of Oriental Studies named after Abu Raykhan Beruni of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, were prepared in a size of about 60 x 30 cm. Each book weighs about 10 kg. Thus, we can note that scribes and calligraphers were especially involved in the book preparation work in the conditions where manual copying of books was the only means of preserving the tradition of manuscript books. [6] They copied books for themselves, for educational and scientific purposes, or out of hobby interest. Bookmakers had different ways of organizing their work. First of all, these books were the product of the calligrapher's work, working individually or together with his students in his home workshop. Books were made in special workshops. In cases where calligraphy workshops engaged professional calligraphers from abroad to fulfill orders, they objectively began to fulfill the functions of corporate-type enterprise associations producing manuscript books.

Here are the calligraphers who worked mainly for the market. relatively stable enterprise associations of lavvohs and sakhhofs. also. The palace and state libraries, where the book masters worked on the preparation of books of high artistic level according to the orders of the tsars and courtiers, should be noted separately.

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